

BREASTFEEDING - WAYS, BREASTFEEDING RECOMMENDATIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6081129>

Yuldasheva Nargiza

To'raqulova Dilfuza

*Teachers of the Technical College of Public Health
named after Abu Ali ibn Sino*

Abstract: *Breastfeeding is a very important period in the life of a mother and child. But sooner or later, it will come to an end. What should be done to wean the baby, at what age does breastfeeding go without crying and whimsy? How do experts recommend weaning a baby?*

Key words: *Breastfeeding, mother, milk, time, pediatricians, psychologists
About methods of weaning the baby:*

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), a breastfed baby under 6 months of age does not need any other type of food or water. However, in time, breast milk will not be enough for the baby's normal development. The baby's diet will then include additional food, followed by a complete meal - an adult diet. At the same time, many mothers ask the question: when and how to stop breastfeeding, how to choose the right time?

At what age is it recommended to wean a child?

Modern pediatricians, psychologists, and breastfeeding counselors recommend breastfeeding a baby for as long as possible, but not until the appropriate age. Usually this age is one and a half, rarely two years. Some mothers continue to breastfeed until they are 3-4 years old, citing fear of losing such physical and emotional contact with their children.

According to social surveys, the optimal time for mothers to wean their children is the time when the child is mentally and physically ready to be weaned, which is approximately one year of age. Many women stop breastfeeding when their baby is one year old and explain why:

The child is now allowed to eat absolutely "adult" food, with certain restrictions;

Decreased levels of essential vitamins and nutrients in breast milk;

Need to get started;

They are tired of feeling like a "dairy factory".

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

HOW TO SEPARATE A BABY FROM MILK?

In some mothers, the process of weaning is almost easy and painless, while in some mothers, the baby does not agree with the decision and begins to be irritable. To make it as easy as possible to wean the baby, it is necessary to gradually switch to breastfeeding 1-2 times a day, only in the morning and in the evening, so that the baby does not need to breastfeed during the day. The mother's body gradually reduces milk production, and the breast does not "swell". In this case, it is enough for the child to sleep for a few nights with another family member, separately from his mother. Advantages of this method:

The baby does not smell breast milk;

His father or grandmother may soothe him, rub him, and give him water or compote;

The mother does not have to choose between weaning or breastfeeding.

If the baby is accustomed to breastfeeding after each feeding, then abrupt cessation of breastfeeding can adversely affect the baby and even lead to hysteria. In this case, the method of weaning is different. It is necessary to deprive the child of breastfeeding during the day for a while, to distract him with delicious juice, compote, clean water, and only then it will be possible to wean the child from evening breastfeeding. There are also other recommendations:

Change breastfeeding habits: breastfeed in situations that are not normal for the baby, such as breastfeeding to the left instead of to the right;

Change breastfeeding times;

Use other perfumes, if the child does not smell the odors, he becomes alienated and begins to eat less.

Some mothers sometimes decide to stop breastfeeding suddenly, leaving the baby in the care of a grandmother or relative for a few days. During this time, the baby "forgets" the breast without seeing the mother and stops asking for it constantly. If a woman suddenly decides not to breastfeed, the following is recommended to avoid problems:

Reducing the amount of fluid you drink during the day;

Restrict hot meals;

Wearing tight underwear;

To relieve swollen breast pain, to reduce the stagnation and accumulation of milk in the breast, to milk it slowly until the milk is fully returned.

If the lactation process cannot be stopped naturally, it is necessary to consult a gynecologist and together with the doctor to choose a drug to stop the production of milk in the body.

ЧЕЛЯБИНСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ
ИНСТИТУТ КУЛЬТУРЫ

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

REFERENCES:

1. M.F.Ziyayeva. Z.O.Rizayeva. "Bolalarda hamshiralik parvarishi". Toshkent, "Fan va texnologiya" 2012 yil.
2. X.N Fayziyev. « Сестринский уход за детьми » Toshkent, «Ilm ziyo» nashriyoti, 2008 yil
3. K.S Inomov. «Pediatriyada hamshiralik ishi» Toshkent, 2007 yil
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. <https://mymedic.uz/>